

"The Jews and the Jesuits" run the world: historic and current narratives of conspiracy in the religious milieu

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This paper will present these theories and their narratives through Latvian case studies. The paper is prepared in the project No. lzp-2023/1-0142. "Genealogy of conspiratoriality in 20th-century Latvia", funded by the Latvian Council of Science

Geoffrey Cubitt analyzing the nature of the theories of conspiracy has written: “Conspiracy theory although it projects a simplistic vision of politics, is not an uncomplex thing. Conspiracy theory is a framework of disparate elements brought and held together, and the relationship between the framework and the elements is both complicated and unclear. Conspiracy theories seldom spring into existence fully formed however, a conspiracy theory that has survived for long in a developed form creates an influence that attracts new influences and molds older ones.”¹ Robert Aleksander Maryks in the context of this research topic, calls it as “a *trans*-Jesuit historiography.”²

The history of the Jesuit order is neither easily explained, nor interpreted, nor described. It is full of secular, religious and ecclesiastical politics, human and confessional prejudices, intrigues, as well – conspiracies. Just like the Jewish, Templar, Zionist history is full of various conspiracies that prevail over professional historiography. The historiography of Jesuit history is full of conspiracies, prejudices, exaggerations and political engagements, especially paying attention to the entanglement of historical discourses of myths and stereotypes left by the Reformation and the religious wars of the 17th century and the era of Confessionalism in the historiography of the order's history. The greatest variety of stereotypes and conspiracies regarding the Jesuit order can be found in the Protestant Western and Northern Europe of the 16th-18th centuries, in the Slavophil school of history of the Russian Empire in the second half of the 19th century and in the historiography of Church history of the Soviet era, where an extremely negative image of the Jesuit is often dominant. The Roman Catholic historiography sometimes is even more suspicious and marginalized, articulating the negative image of Jesuits in the historic perspective and nowadays.

¹ Cubitt, Geoffrey, *The Jesuit Myth: Conspiracy Theory and Politics in Nineteenth-Century France* (Oxford, 1993; online edn, Oxford Academic)

² Robert Aleksander Maryks, “Idźcież już precz!” [Come on, get out already!]: The Origins and Development of the Earliest Anti-Jesuit Literature in the Commonwealth of Poland–Lithuania, 1577–1614, *Journal of Jesuit Studies*, Volume 10, Issue 2023, pg. 26-44

In the book "Evaluation of the Council of Trent" by Martin Chemnitz, a follower of Martin Luther, pastor and German theologian, wrote in 1565: "...this sect which was recently founded by the Roman pontiff for the purpose of destroying the Churches that convert people to the pure teaching of the Gospel..."³ As the world-renowned historian, John O'Malley, has said: "Called devils and saints, the Jesuits have contributed to the emergence of these extreme characterizing interpretations during the more than 450 years of the order's existence. Over time, relatively balanced views have been established in historiography, but they always have their own national, cultural or religious conditions. Jesuit history cannot be separated from so - called the Counter-Reformation era and the Jesuits have always been seen as emblematic of everything good and bad that happened in that era."⁴

For example, in the Latvian/Baltic or "German European" historiography, one can find radically different interpretations of the history of the Jesuit order. One of the most interesting work is called "anti-Jesuita" which was published in two parts by the most prominent representative of Lutheran orthodoxy in Swedish Livonia and generally in the entire Protestant Europe - Hermann Samson (*Hermannus Samsonius*) in 1615. He declared Jesuits as demons and accused them in all of conspiracies of that particular era and milieu. Sometimes his narrative is very close to medieval theories of Jewish conspiracy, just substituting communities and places, even borrowing ideas and terms (Jewish Sabbath versus Jesuit Sabbath).

The epithets of the Russian Orthodox and Slavophil historians about the evil dogs and spies of the Pope are just as vivid in the epithets, but the term "Jesuit" is often used in a negative sense, even in the modern Russian language. Soviet ideology added its deeply ideological and anti-Catholic and anti-Vatican perspective in its propaganda, constructing the new images of Jesuits as anti-Soviet army force hold and commanded by Vatican and rejuvenating few other old – fashioned images of Jesuits as mediators and supporters of the new world. Often nowadays, all these interpretations and conspiracies coexist in the historical and cultural-historical memory worldwide, get into conflicts or complement each other. The same theories and narratives could be found all across the world with few cultural exceptions. As Andrew McKenzie-McHarg has explained: "Yet history also has a lot more to offer than simply the message "we've seen it all before." Turning to the past reveals both congruence and incongruence and can therefore clarify what is genuinely new and unprecedented about the contemporary moment we are fated to inhabit."⁵

The history of the Jesuit order began at the crossroads of the middle ages and modern times. It was a very complicated time in the world history. It was a time of religious, political, cultural and spiritual crisis and transformations: religious wars,

³ Jonathan Wright. *God's Soldiers. Adventures, Politics, Intrigue and Power. A History of the Jesuits.* Doubleday, NY, London, Toronto, Sydney, Auckland, 2004, pg. 13.

⁴ John W. O'Malley. *The First Jesuits.* Harvard, 1993, pg. 2

⁵ McKenzie-McHarg, A. (2023). Jesuits, Conspiracies, and Conspiracy Theories. *Journal of Jesuit Studies*, 10(1), 15-25. <https://doi.org/10.1163/22141332-10010003>

discover of Americas, collapse of the “unified West and Western Christian Church” etc. The old world was dead, but the new one has not yet emerged.

Since its founding by Ignatius of Loyola in 1540, the Society of Jesus—more commonly known as the Jesuits—has played a critical role in the events of modern history. Markus Friedrich describes Jesuits that has deftly walked a tightrope between sacred and secular involvement and experienced difficulties during changing times, all while shaping cultural developments from pastoral care and spirituality to art, education, and science. The order shaped the culture of the Counter-Reformation and participated in the establishment of European empires, including missionary activity throughout Asia and in many parts of Africa in the sixteenth and seventeenth centuries. The Jesuits often tangled with the Roman Curia and the pope, resulting in their suppression in 1773, but the order returned in 1814 to rise again to a powerful position of influence.⁶ Jesuits were neither a monolithic group, nor national community. One of the first Jesuits Jarome Nadal (once converted Jew) once said: “The world is our house. He was referring, on one level, to the world outside of churches and monasteries, but also to the multitudes of God’s people and the expanse of human cultures. As Jesuit leaders explained at their General Congregation in 2008 - the entire world becomes the object of our interest and concern.”⁷

From the middle ages, Jesuits took the features of the scholastic worldview, and from the Renaissance - humanistic methods and a broad vision of the world, connecting and blending the two eras into one, creating their own method, a special worldview, and a new type of Christian spirituality, whose main guiding principle was "to be contemplative in action." Even Ignatius of Loyola himself, the founder of the Jesuit order, was a typical child of these eras, who understood the shortcomings and positive sides of the scholastic era and was not afraid of new challenges of the Renaissance and humanist ideas. The world and society at the end of the 15th century and the beginning of the 16th century, along with new geographical and scientific discoveries, religious wars and their consequences, experienced great internal and external transformations. Great geographical discoveries changed the boundaries and mental map of European Christian civilization, scientific discoveries - the relationship between man and the natural/material world, and religious wars - began to undermine faith in God, the Church and man himself. Under the influence of these transformations, a large part of people and European societies felt confused, lost their landmarks and lived in certain eschatological moods, where there was no room left for hope and optimism for the future.

The suppression of the Society of Jesus took place in 1773 during the papacy of Clement XIV. The most famous conspiracies now were spread by the official Roman Catholic Church and its believers. Andrew McKenzie-McHarg has underlined that since the 1750s the Society found itself besieged on numerous fronts by diverse opponents making multifarious accusations. Prominent among these accusations was the charge of conspiracy. In the late 1750s, this accusation found new traction in two assassination attempts, one targeting King Louis XV of France (r.1715–74) in January

⁶ Markus Friedrich. *The Jesuits. A History*. Princeton University Press, 2023, pg1

⁷ <https://www.jesuits.global/about-us/our-history/>

1757 and another directed at King Joseph of Portugal (r.1750–77) in September 1758. Yet in addition to reanimating thoroughly routinized charges of Jesuit complicity in these crimes, some opponents of the order began to frame such allegations within imputations of an even more profound subversion. If the Jesuits had been charged with conspiracy in the past, now they found themselves increasingly confronted with the denunciation that the order itself was a conspiracy.⁸ As the historian Dale K. Van Kley writes in the conclusion of a recent essay, the Society of Jesus had come to resemble “a conspiracy reduced to a system” in which “each Jesuit [was] a conspirator by definition.”⁹

Geoffrey Cubitt in his book “The Jesuit Myth: Conspiracy Theory and Politics in Nineteenth – Century France” pointed out that theories on Jesuit conspiracy was extremely influential in Europe and particularly in early and mid-19th century France, circulating in the circles of the French secular politics and supported by the secular literature, fiction and left wing political parties.¹⁰ The political and religious Left and the Right was fascinated with the various theories on conspiracy. All declared political war against Jesuits and Free Masons creating: “...French politics surrounded by alarmism and complacency that dramatized insecurities and systematized mistrust and encouraged the habit of rhetorical intransigence and moral ostracism that bedeviled French public debate on several occasions during the century and the Revolution. The impending fear and the division of opinions on the nature of the conspiracy theory denied progress and improvement of the human affairs and the inherent openness of historical outcomes instead it encouraged politics of confrontation and exclusion.”¹¹

If certain theories of conspiracy have entered and found its long-lasting place in the world-wide historiographies and fiction genre, than genealogy of the development of these theories in academic tradition usually remain silent. Only few experts in “Jesuitics” have underlined this issue. Where and how it started?

In the early 17th century, a former Jesuit promulgated the “Monita Privata/Secreta,” or “Secret Instructions of the Jesuits,” in which superior general of the Society of Jesus Claudio Acquaviva (1573-1615) supposedly instructs Jesuits on how to expand their wealth and power: “Princes and persons of distinction everywhere must by all means be so managed, that we may have their ear, and that will easily secure their hearts,” begins one chapter. “All persons will become our creatures, and no one will dare to give the society the least disquiet or opposition.”¹² Former Polish Jesuit Hieronim Zahorowski (1582–1634) published a work that would

⁸ McKenzie-McHarg, A. (2023). Jesuits, Conspiracies, and Conspiracy Theories. *Journal of Jesuit Studies*, 10(1), 15-25. <https://doi.org/10.1163/22141332-10010003>

⁹ McKenzie-McHarg, A. (2023). Jesuits, Conspiracies, and Conspiracy Theories. *Journal of Jesuit Studies*, 10(1), 15-25. <https://doi.org/10.1163/22141332-10010003>

¹⁰ Cubitt, Geoffrey, *The Jesuit Myth: Conspiracy Theory and Politics in Nineteenth-Century France* (Oxford, 1993; online edn, Oxford Academic, 3 Oct. 2011), <https://doi.org/10.1093/acprof:oso/9780198228684.001.0001>, accessed 5 June 2024.

¹¹ Cubitt, Geoffrey, *The Jesuit Myth: Conspiracy Theory and Politics in Nineteenth-Century France* (Oxford, 1993; online edn, Oxford Academic, 3 Oct. 2011), <https://doi.org/10.1093/acprof:oso/9780198228684.001.0001>, accessed 5 June 2024.

¹² <https://www.americamagazine.org/arts-culture/2022/06/14/jesuit-conspiracy-theory-great-replacement-243137>

have a long-lasting impact, creating most of the stereotypes and myths that still exist and circulate around the world “in space and time.” Zahorowski attended a Jesuit college in Poznan, converted from Orthodox Christianity to Roman Catholicism, and entered the Society of Jesus; he did not pass the examination, which meant that he would not be permitted to take the fourth vow of the order. It did allow him to be ordained and would exclude him from occupying higher level offices in the order.¹³ Zahorowski began to write anonymous letters specifically targeting sons of the Polish nobility, urging them to attend “better” schools than Jesuit ones. Zahorowski’s identity as the author of the letters was discovered and he was expelled from the Society in 1613. Using his inside knowledge of the Society, Zahorowski decided to write an “exposé” of the internal workings of the order-filtered through his own disappointments.¹⁴

Jim McDermott, S.J., is an associate editor at “America” summing up all of the Jesuit conspiracies that have existed and still circulate in the USA has expressed: “Over the course of its nearly 500 years of existence, the Society of Jesus has been the subject of many conspiracy theories of its own. Jesuits have been accused of killing Abraham Lincoln and John F. Kennedy; we’ve been painted as doomsday cultists trying to bring about the end times and as maintaining our own secret global cabal, they were from another planet, but no, those gray creatures were made by Jesuits doing science in our “deep underground military bases.”¹⁵ Illusion of Jesuits being soldiers (God’s soldiers – reference to the age of chivalry and Ignatius’s early background) on the mystical and stereotypical level have made many links to any other phenomenon of militarism and its connection with Jesuit order, including various 20th century authoritarian and totalitarian regimes (Bolshevism, Nazism, Fascism), as well Zionism. Paradoxically enough, but those regimes have created their own myth and theories of Jesuit conspiracies with the long lasting effect. One of those fancy theories tell us about “Jewish – Jesuit and Bolshevik” conspiracies and the new world order that being to be globally implemented. It has appeared in the Hitler’s circles among the first stock Nazis in 20s of 30th century. One of the earliest ideological influences on Adolf Hitler was Johann Dietrich Eckart (1868–1923). Eckart was a poet, playwright, and journalist over the course of his lifetime. Eckart’s book *Der Bolschewismus von Moses bis Lenin: Zwiegespräch zwischen Hitler und mir (1923)* became influential in the Nazi circles, but the book itself is based on the approach of conversation between and Hitler and author: “The subject, of course, is an exploration of the history of the Jewish question. Yet, even within this supposed dialogue (there is debate whether Hitler ever spoke the words attributed to him in the work), we can also find disparaging remarks about Catholicism and its purported links with the Jews.”¹⁶

¹³ Griech-Poelle, B. A. (2018). Jesuits, Jews, Christianity, and Bolshevism: An Existential Threat to Germany?. *Journal of Jesuit Studies*, 5(1), 33-53. <https://doi.org/10.1163/22141332-00501003>

¹⁴ Griech-Poelle, B. A. (2018). Jesuits, Jews, Christianity, and Bolshevism: An Existential Threat to Germany?. *Journal of Jesuit Studies*, 5(1), 33-53. <https://doi.org/10.1163/22141332-00501003>

¹⁵ <https://www.americamagazine.org/arts-culture/2022/06/14/jesuit-conspiracy-theory-great-replacement-243137>

¹⁶ Griech-Poelle, B. A. (2018). Jesuits, Jews, Christianity, and Bolshevism: An Existential Threat to Germany?. *Journal of Jesuit Studies*, 5(1), 33-53. <https://doi.org/10.1163/22141332-00501003>

Hitler outlining how the Catholic Church has been polluted by Jewish infiltration. “There have been popes of Jewish blood. Also there has seldom been or never been a shortage of other dignitaries of the same descent in the church. Was that which they stood for Catholicism? No, it was Judaism. Let’s take just one thing: the selling of indulgences. The very essence of the Jewish spirit.” The Catholic Church is portrayed as having been invaded, taken over, and ruled by Jews. Conspiracy theories abound: “But he also works from the inside, where he is even more dangerous, in the mask of the Christian minister. The Christian confessions swarm with Jewish and half-Jewish clergymen.”—Finally, the pamphlet ends with the dire warning: “one can only understand the Jew when one knows what his ultimate goal is. And that goal is, beyond world domination, the annihilation of the world.”¹⁷

The image of the Jews masquerading as Christian leaders included attacks on Ignatius of Loyola himself. In the same edition of 1937, readers of *Der Stürmer* would have found (on page fourteen) a large-sized picture of Ignatius. The caption under the picture reads, “Baptized Jew: Founder of the Jesuit Order.” The imagery and caption of Ignatius is meant to insert doubt into the mind of the readers: if the founder of the Jesuits was a baptized Jew (he was not), then perhaps many of the Jesuits were indeed working towards the same goals as the Jews.¹⁸

One of the most prominent (Baltic born) Nazi ideologist Alfred Rosenberg saw the Jesuits as running the Vatican and utilizing their power to destroy potential reformers within the church. Taking a page out of the *Monita*, Rosenberg was drawing on the well-developed stereotypes of Jesuits as cunning, ruthless, and absolutely bent on ruling. Here again one can see how Rosenberg has placed Catholic priests, led by Jesuits in Rome, into the category of internal enemies, seeking to destroy the German fatherland. Eckart and Rosenberg were influential in helping Hitler develop his ideas concerning Jews, Christianity.

Rosenberg elaborates: “The heaviest blow that ever struck humanity was the coming of Christianity. Bolshevism is Christianity’s illegitimate child. Both are inventions of the Jew. The deliberate lie in the matter of religion was introduced into the world by Christianity. Bolshevism practices a lie of the same nature, when it claims to bring liberty to men, whereas in reality it seeks only to enslave them. Hitler believed that the Jesuits knew that they are preaching lies in order to gain control over people, linking Jesuits, Jews, Catholics, and Bolsheviks together.”¹⁹

The various theories of conspiracy related to the Jews and Jesuits and the construction of their world order often are used in the certain religious and secular circles to explain the world order and controlling power. These controlling and governing institutions in the narratives of conspiracy theories are the centers of world economic, religious and political power. Very often historically and currently, Jews and Jesuits have been understood as joint power. Beth Ann Griech-Polelle underlines that

¹⁷ Griech-Polelle, B. A. (2018). Jesuits, Jews, Christianity, and Bolshevism: An Existential Threat to Germany?. *Journal of Jesuit Studies*, 5(1), 33-53. <https://doi.org/10.1163/22141332-00501003>

¹⁸ Griech-Polelle, B. A. (2018). Jesuits, Jews, Christianity, and Bolshevism: An Existential Threat to Germany?. *Journal of Jesuit Studies*, 5(1), 33-53. <https://doi.org/10.1163/22141332-00501003>

¹⁹ Griech-Polelle, B. A. (2018). Jesuits, Jews, Christianity, and Bolshevism: An Existential Threat to Germany. *Journal of Jesuit Studies*, 5(1), 33-53. <https://doi.org/10.1163/22141332-00501003>

“Adolf Hitler, Alfred Rosenberg, Dietrich Eckart, and others connect Jesuits to Jews in their writings and speeches, conflating Catholicism and Judaism with Bolshevism, pinpointing Jesuits as supposedly being a part of the larger “Judeo-Bolshevik conspiracy” aiming to destroy the German people.” (2018) The Jesuits impacted by this Nazi directive correctly identified it as an attempt on the part of the Nazi regime to place Jesuits into the same category of other persecuted groups in German society such as the Jews, the mentally ill and physically handicapped, the Roma and the Sinti, and criminals.

After the World War II and defeat of the Third Reich, Jesuit conspiracies have not left public “false news” discourse. Jesuits have been accused of hiding Nazis, planning to assassinate JFK, John Paul II (Polish pontiff had very complicated relations with the Jesuit order and was planning for the second time in the history of order to suppress it), promoting the state of Israel and helping to establish the Jewish reign and control over the world. Very often theories of the Jesuit conspiracy are reaching its popularity with the rise of anti-Semitic theories. For example, the new spark of these theories have been flooding the literature, social accounts and media when Francis (the First Jesuit pope)²⁰ who was one of the promoter of the Christian – Judeo religious dialogue in the South of America, was elected as pope in March, 2013 but gained its greater visibility when pontifex visited Israel in May, 2014. Visiting Holocaust memorial Yad Vashem in Jerusalem, Francis laid a wreath of yellow and white flowers in the Hall of Remembrance and then kissed the hands of the six Holocaust survivors in a sign of humility and honor as he heard their stories and of loved ones killed by the Nazis during World War II.²¹ Kissing hands of Holocaust survivors was interpreted as the sign of obedience, loyalty and service to Jews by the Jesuit pope. These allegations were very strong among in the general anti-Semitic circles and Christian anti-Semitic circles of the various new age and sectarian groups. A former Utah tech executive Dave Bateman (ex-Mormon) said that he believed Pope Francis was secretly a Jewish agent installed to help distribute the COVID-19 vaccine around the world in an effort to create "totalitarian rule."²²

Short summary

Ironically and sarcastically enough, but Jesuit and Journalist Jim McDermott has said that from its origins, the Society of Jesus had been an international organization with men placed amongst the powerful and a founder who had said we should be trying to influence the influential. Conspiracy theories about the Jesuits trying to rule the world kept popping up because what we were doing looked a lot like that. The anti-Jesuit hysteria meant to attack in historical and current day perspective, not only single order, but also their missions, organizations, schools, Universities

²⁰ Election of the first Jesuit pope have spark very many theories of the Jesuit conspiracy that was justified with the prophecies and eschatological narratives. The prophecy of the Malachy on the last pope and “the Black Peter”

²¹ <https://www.worldjewishcongress.org/en/news/in-jerusalem-pope-kisses-hands-of-six-shoah-survivors-pays-respects-to-terror-victims>

²² <https://www.newsweek.com/gop-donor-claims-pope-francis-jewish-agent-installed-distribute-vaccine-1665640>

and lay-collaborators, sometimes even strongly promoted by the radical and conservative wing Catholics and their sectarian groups. Often linked with the anti-Semitic sentiments and anti-Israeli politics when all current modern day sociopolitical, religious, spiritual and cultural transformations and cataclysms have been seen and explained in the conspiracy world –view.